

Ecological implications of deep pruning: a case report on Persian squirrel nesting in a centennial olive grove on the island of Lesbos, Greece

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Abstract: In recent years, traditional olive groves have undergone a shift towards modern farming practices, raising concerns about their potential impact on local fauna. Despite the documented effects of various agricultural practices on wildlife, there is a notable gap in understanding the implications of pruning practices in traditional olive groves. This study presents a unique observation, the first documented adverse effect of pruning on an olive tree within a traditional grove in Lesbos, Greece, inhabited by Persian squirrels (*Sciurus anomalus*). Beyond immediate impacts, we conducted comprehensive measurements of both the pruned olive tree and the squirrel's nest (den), along with an assessment of the entire grove. The findings highlight the need for ecologically informed olive grove management to sustain biodiversity in these historically significant environments.

Keywords: Caucasian squirrel, centennial olive trees, nesting locality, threat, traditional olive groves

Introduction

Centennial olive groves exhibit resilience in the face of challenges posed by global agriculture, a primary driver of biodiversity loss (Dudley & Alexander, 2017). These groves not only contribute to agricultural resources but also embody cultural heritage by preserving biodiversity and shaping landscapes (Loumou & Giourga, 2003; Kostelenos & Kiritsakis, 2017; Zevgolis et al., 2023a). Moreover, they play a pivotal role as habitats for diverse fauna species, providing shelter, optimal survival conditions, and a dependable food source (Calabrese et al., 2012).

However, the rise of modernisation in agriculture has resulted in the deterioration of natural habitats, se-

verely limiting the living spaces of numerous fauna species (Gibbs et al., 2009; Wilcove & Koh, 2010). Amidst the broad threats posed by various agricultural sectors (Katayama et al., 2015; Morgado et al., 2020), an exploration of specialised agricultural practices tied to traditional crops at a local level reveals an equally crucial aspect. This sector, although less studied, significantly contributes to the complex landscape of challenges faced by biodiversity (Christopoulos & Pafilis, 2021; Michael et al., 2021; Zevgolis & Christopoulos, 2023).

In recent years, there has been a notable rise in the adoption of modern farming practices including the implementation of more intensive pruning techniques (Abenavoli & Marcianò, 2013; Camposeo et al.,

2023). This shift has prompted concerns regarding its impact on various fauna species inhabiting olive groves, as there is a wide range of documented impacts resulting from olive grove management systems (Morgado et al., 2020; Pérez et al., 2023), olive fruit harvesting practices (Zevgolis & Christopoulos, 2023), plant protection and pest control measures (Christopoulos & Pafilis, 2021), and soil tillage (Sánchez-Fernández et al., 2020; Simoni et al., 2021). Interestingly, despite these documented effects, there is a notable absence of information addressing the consequences of deep pruning on fauna inhabiting traditional olive groves.

In Greece, where olives are harvested from October to March, pruning olive trees is an essential practice that enhances productivity and tree health (Connor et al., 2014). Nevertheless, it is essential to underscore a specific practice that has surfaced in response to challenges like land abandonment, economic recession, and the substantial costs linked to olive collection. Across various regions in Greece, there is a growing inclination towards deep pruning of olive trees, primarily driven by the intention to sell the pruned wood for use as firewood (pers. obs.). This strategy while addressing economic considerations and resource utilisation (Troumbis & Zevgolis, 2020), has adverse effects on the species that rely on olive trees for nesting.

One such species, recognised as a keystone species in Greece, is a southwest Asian tree squirrel, the Persian squirrel, *Sciurus anomalus* (Rodentia: Sciuridae). Greece and in particular the island of Lesbos, being the westernmost extent of its global distribution, serves as the exclusive location for this particular Asian mammal species in Europe (Koprowski et al., 2016). The species is considered Near Threatened as it is included in the National Red Data Book in Greece (Legakis & Maragou, 2009), facing threats such as habitat loss, road network expansion, wildfires, and feral cats (Yigit et al., 2016; Zevgolis et al., 2023c). In the eastern parts of its distribution range, additional threats include habitat loss, fragmentation, and poaching (Yigit et al., 2016; Aidek et al., 2022; Aghbolaghi et al., 2023).

Here we report for the first time an adverse effect of the impact of pruning practices on an olive tree of a traditional olive grove on the island of Lesbos, Greece on a family of Persian squirrels. The Persian squirrel, maintains a close association with the traditional olive groves of the island, playing a vital role in areas

where these groves are often with other tree species along field edges, streamsides, or near settlements (Zannetos et al., 2022; pers. obs.). Given the unusualness of this observation, our investigation extends beyond the immediate impact, involving measurements of both the olive tree and the den (a squirrel's nest) characteristics, along with an assessment of the entire traditional olive grove.

Materials and methods

Study area

The island of Lesbos, Greece, situated in the northern Aegean Sea near the coast of Asia Minor, has a longstanding tradition of cultivating olive trees (Marathianou et al., 2000; Kizos and Koulouri, 2006), which dominate over 85% of the island's agricultural area (Zevgolis et al., 2021). The majority of these groves consist of century-old trees (Zevgolis et al., 2023b), many of which adhere to traditional practices, contributing to attracting a variety of fauna species (Calabrese et al., 2012; Kabassi et al., 2021; Llorca et al., 2023), including Persian squirrels (Zannetos et al., 2022), offering them shelter and suitable nesting sites.

Olive tree, den, and grove metrics

In the context of our ongoing research initiative since 2014, which centers on comprehending the ecological dynamics of the Persian squirrel within the island ecosystem and concurrently addresses the conservation of traditional olive groves, our attention was redirected due to an incident on 6 April 2023. The incident, wherein a local olive worker reported the discovery of two abandoned juvenile squirrels during the pruning of an olive tree, and as a result their active den, prompted an immediate response from our research team. To thoroughly assess the situation, a field visit was promptly organised to the specific location in the region of Larsos (39°7'32.25"N, 26°28'57.75"E) (Fig. 1). Upon reaching the site, detailed observations were conducted to scrutinise the pruning practices implemented by the local worker.

Following the observational phase, we systematically measured key characteristics of the olive tree hosting the squirrels' den. This included

Fig. 1. Distribution map of the main land cover types along with the locality of the incident on the island of Lesvos, Greece.

height (H , m), diameter (DBH, cm), the age of the olive tree (Arnan et al., 2012), and the presence and quantity of cavities within its trunk. Thereafter, we further proceeded to conduct an in-depth examination of the active den. This included the determination of the den's height on the tree (H_{den}) and an assessment of its location, specifically whether it was situated on the main trunk or branches. Additionally, we counted den's entrances (holes), examined its aspect, and measured its vertical (VCD, cm), horizontal (HCD, cm), and internal diameter (ICD, cm) (Zevgolis et al., 2022). Furthermore, we collected the nesting material found inside the den and calculated its dry biomass.

To comprehensively assess the habitat surrounding the den locality, we utilised ArcGIS 10.2 software (ESRI Inc., Redlands, CA, USA). A 50 m radius circular plot, centered on the den, was created to capture the immediate environment effectively. This selection was based on approximations of the

“core area” actively utilised by Persian squirrels (Zannetos et al., 2022; Zevgolis et al., 2023c), representing an area where each animal is likely to spend all or most of its annual cycle. Within this circular plot, we extracted data concerning the olive grove's total area and we calculated the mean olive tree cover density using Copernicus high-resolution layers (EEA, 2020). Furthermore, we conducted a comprehensive analysis that encompassed measuring the total number of olive trees, categorising them into pruned and unpruned, and assessing the aspect and slope of the grove. Additionally, we recorded detailed information about woody vegetation within the grove.

Results

Our investigation revealed that the deep pruning techniques employed had profoundly altered the structure of the olive tree, disrupting the squirrel's

Fig. 2. The traditional olive grove in the region of Larsos, Lesvos, Greece: (a, b, c) The section of the grove subjected to deep pruning, including the olive tree from which the juvenile squirrels were found; (d, e) the segment of the grove left undisturbed (unpruned).

nesting site and prompting the mother to abandon both the den and her juvenile offspring. Recognising the need for specialised care, we immediately sent the juvenile squirrels to a wildlife rehabilitation centre.

Regarding the squirrel's habitat, the traditional olive grove, in which the incident took place, encompassed a total area of 5.9 ha, characterised by an average slope of 12.7%, and situated at a mean elevation of 63 m (a.s.l.). The landscape featured diverse ecological infrastructures, including terraces and dry-stone walls, contributing to the traditional character of the grove's structure. The grove had also scattered broadleaf trees including kermes oak (*Quercus coccifera*), common fig (*Ficus carica*), and pomegranate (*Punica granatum*), along with a few conifer trees (*Pinus brutia*) in the north-eastern part of the grove.

Among the total number of olive trees ($n = 527$) within the grove, more than half ($n = 267$) had undergone extensive pruning, including the olive tree upon which the juvenile Persian squirrels were discovered (Figure 2c). This deep pruning process involved the total removal of branches and foliage, leading to a significant alteration in the structural composition of the olive trees (Fig. 2a, b, c).

Within the 50 m plot, we identified a total of 70 olive trees, comprising 31 that underwent deep

pruning and 39 that remained unpruned. The measured metrics of the pruned olive trees indicated significant changes compared to unpruned counterparts typically found in traditional olive groves and in the unpruned part of this particular grove. These pruned trees exhibited a noticeable reduction in height, and their overall appearance suggested an almost complete absence of canopy, in stark contrast to the denser and more closed structure typically observed in unpruned olive trees (Fig. 2d, e). In fact, the 31 deep-pruned trees had a mean H of 3.97 ± 0.45 m and a mean DBH of 71.28 ± 32.12 cm, while the unpruned trees displayed a mean H of 7.17 ± 2.34 m and a mean DBH of 73.44 ± 29.46 cm. Assessing the age of these trees, the deep-pruned ones had a mean age of 239.33 ± 56.71 years, while the unpruned ones showed a slightly higher mean age of 243.88 ± 51.09 years. Regarding olive tree density within the plot, there were 89.17 trees per hectare. The mean olive tree cover density was 81.34%, with the remaining space between olive trees comprising scattered kermes oaks.

The olive tree, where the Persian squirrels were found, had the second bigger H and DBH from all the neighbouring trees within the plot. In fact the tree exhibited a trunk height (until the first pruned branches) of 2.45 m with a total H of 8.95 m (we

Fig. 3. The pruned olive tree in which the den was found: (a, b) the two entrances in the main trunk along with food remains (olive fruit); (c) the vertical projection of the pruned branch; (d) the pruned branch containing the den; (e) the nesting material found inside the den.

added the height of the longest pruned branch to the trunk height) and a DBH of 77.7 cm. Moreover, the tree exhibited a total of nine cavities.

The abandoned den was discovered on the ground next to the base of this particular olive tree. The den, prior to pruning, was located on a branch that had been completely cut from the tree, suggesting that the nest was destroyed during the pruning process (Fig. 3). As per our observations and information from the olive worker, the den was positioned on the main branch of the tree at approximately $H_{\text{den}} = 7.1$ m above ground. The den featured three entrances (holes), with two situated in the main trunk of the tree, one at 15 cm above ground and the second at 75 cm above ground. The third entrance was located on the main branch, with a VCD of 12 cm, a HCD of 13 cm, and an ICD of

35 cm. Exploring the pruned branch that housed the den, we discovered nesting material composed of olive leaves and wood chips, amounting to 143.47 g of dry biomass (Fig. 3).

Discussion

In this study, we present a significant observation, offering a unique and valuable perspective on the potential consequences of deep pruning on Persian squirrel nesting dynamics. While this single observation may not provide definitive evidence of a widespread impact of deep pruning on Persian squirrel nesting dynamics, it nonetheless serves as a critical piece of evidence in the ongoing assessment

of the species' conservation status. The significance of this documentation is heightened due to the Near Threatened status of Persian squirrels in Greece (Legakis & Maragou, 2009), indicating that the species requires monitoring and conservation efforts to prevent it from moving into a more critical category. Given the notably low estimated population on the island of Lesbos, ranging from 500 to 3000 mature individuals (European Topic Centre on Biological Diversity, 2015), and considering previously identified stressors of the species (Zannetos et al., 2022; Zevgolis et al., 2023c), it becomes unmistakably clear that the Persian squirrel is confronted with a convergence of challenges, underscoring the need for mitigative measures to forestall an exacerbation of vulnerability levels within the population.

The revelation of the detrimental effects of deep pruning on the reproductive ecology of the Persian squirrel, even with this single observation, underscores the need to re-evaluate and potentially discontinue extensive pruning practices within traditional olive groves. The widespread occurrence of deep pruning, evident in over half of the olive trees in the study area, raises concerns about the potential for disruption of suitable nesting sites for Persian squirrels. Historically in Lesbos, traditional practices embraced a holistic approach, recognising the interconnectedness of shaping trees, environmental adaptation, and optimising productivity. They involved shaping the trees to achieve significant height and crown area; a strategic adaptation to environmental stress, aimed at fostering the production of larger biennial crops (Zevgolis et al., 2021). However, current agricultural practices on the island, which abruptly modifying the vegetative-productive equilibrium of the olive tree (Zevgolis et al., 2021), not only jeopardises the resilience of the olive trees by compromising their ability to photosynthesise and impacting their overall growth (International Olive Council, 2007) but, as our study highlights, may inadvertently neglect species that depend on varied niches within the tree for shelter and forage by removing potential nesting locations and disrupting established habitats and breeding patterns (Remm & Löhms, 2011; Griffiths et al., 2020).

While the Persian squirrel adapts to various tree-rich environments, its preference for tall and large trees within a dense canopy, particularly the centennial ones as observed in our case, is driven by

the increased availability of food and protection from predators, making such nesting locations ideal for the species (Edelman & Koprowski, 2005; Edelman et al., 2009). Consequently, the locale of this incident stands out among the optimal habitats for the Persian squirrel on the island. The substantial olive tree cover density, coupled with the interspersed space between trees, benefits this particular species, aligning with its more terrestrial habits compared to, for instance, *Sciurus vulgaris* (Koprowski et al., 2016).

The Persian squirrel's vulnerability to various pressures, as demonstrated by this instance of pruning-related impacts, underscores the need for targeted conservation efforts. In light of this incident, we posit that analogous incidents may transpire in regions where deep pruning is employed in olive groves, both within Greece and in other olive-growing countries in which the species is distributed. Consequently, more systematic research of this issue across other countries would be necessary to fully gauge the magnitude of this potential issue. Greece, as the westernmost extent of the species' global distribution, assumes significant responsibility for the preservation of the Persian squirrel. Any pressure or threat to the species demands recording and comprehensive assessment to inform conservation strategies effectively. By recognising and addressing the intricate web of stressors, including those induced by agricultural practices, conservation initiatives can be tailored to safeguard the Persian squirrel and its unique ecological role within traditional olive groves.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, (Y.G.Z.), upon reasonable request.

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